

Land Cover Changes Based on Maps and Satellite Images along the Croatian–Hungarian Section of the Drava River’s Active Floodplain

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Abstract: Despite regulations, dam and embankment constructions upstream, the Drava is among Europe's most preserved near-natural rivers in the Croatian-Hungarian section. We examined how land cover in the active floodplain changed between the date of the first military survey (1783) and 2018. We delimited the study area, which is the area between the flood protection embankments. We did not deal with the flood-protected areas (former floodplain). We georeferenced and vectorized military and civilian topographic maps from the following years: 1783–84, 1859, 1880, 1950–52, and 1990–2000. We also classified a Sentinel satellite image from 2018. We identified the following land cover categories: water area of river channel and standing waters, waterlogged areas (marshes), forest, bush, grassland (meadow, pasture), orchard and vineyard, built-up area. We found that the proportion of near-natural areas (water, marsh, forest) decreased significantly between 1783–84 and 1880, and then increased from then on. The trend of spatial change in agricultural areas was the opposite. Among the landscape ecology indicators, the Number of Patches (NP), Shannon Diversity Index (SHDI), and Edge Density (ED) were lower at the beginning and end of the study period, while they were higher in its middle. The Mean Patch Fractal Dimension (MFRACT) showed an increasing trend.

Keywords: Mura-Drava-Danube Biosphere Reserve; land cover change; GIS.

1 Introduction

The historical-geographical approach to landscapes interprets land use and land cover change as long-term processes in which social, economic, and political factors play a decisive role (Bender et al. 2005). The analysis of historical maps allows for the comparison of pre-industrial and post-industrial conditions, as well as the identification of the disappearance or transformation of traditional land-use patterns (Kocsis and Schweitzer 2011).

Geographic information systems (GIS) enable the integrated management and quantitative analysis of map and remote sensing data from different dates (Longley et al. 2015). Digital spatial data allow for a more precise presentation of changes in spatial patterns (Weng 2009).

The Danube-Drava National Park was established in southern Hungary in 1996, its boundary is formed by the state border for a length of more than 160 km. The Mura-Drava Regional Park was set up in Croatia later, and in 2011 a joint Hungarian-Croatian biosphere reserve was created.

Serbia joined the Mura-Drava-Danube UNESCO Biosphere Reserve in 2017, Slovenia in 2018, and Austria in 2019.

The practical significance of our study lies in its contribution to nature conservation planning, as a significant portion of our study area—32.7%—belongs to the Hungarian Danube-Drava National Park (Duna-Dráva Nemzeti Park Igazgatóság 2026), and the entire area is part of the Mura-Drava-Danube UNESCO Biosphere Reserve (WWF-Austria 2026). A comprehensive understanding of past and present conditions facilitates the implementation of future habitat restoration projects. Areas of higher ecological value can be distinguished from those with lower ecological potential, thereby revealing the state of the ecological network. We analysed the evolution of landscape structure using landscape-level metrics.

2 Description of the study area

The Drava River forms the border between Hungary and Croatia. The selected study area is the current active floodplain between Potony (Detkovac) and Alsószentmárton (Podgajci Podravski), covering an area of 105.5 km² (Figure 1). The boundaries of the study area are marked by flood protection embankments.

The study area is a floodplain, with the study site located at an elevation of 89–110 meters above sea level. The most characteristic landforms are abandoned meanders. The western regions belong to a warm-moderately humid climate zone, while the eastern parts belong to a warm-moderately dry climate zone. The natural vegetation has now been largely fragmented. The larger forest blocks consist mainly of softwood and partly hardwood. Reed beds are associated with former side channels and oxbows, tall grasslands stretch in patches along the flood dykes and close to settlements. The fauna is extremely rich,

Figure 1. The study area is marked in red (background: [openstreetmap.org](https://www.openstreetmap.org)).

with numerous rare, protected, and biogeographically significant species (Dövényi 2010).

3 Materials and methods

The use of historical maps also poses methodological challenges. To analyze changes in land use over the past centuries, it was necessary to coordinate military maps with various projections, scales, and legend keys, as well as satellite imagery, and organize them into a unified framework (Timár and Biszak 2010). Due to changes in legend symbols and land-use categories over time, it was necessary to develop a unified classification system. There are differences in the legend keys between maps created at different times and for different purposes. Therefore, we have merged some categories (e.g., we classified young coppice forests as forests and seasonally flooded sandbars as water bodies) and have separated only the main categories that can be clearly identified on all maps.

We projected the datasets into the same projection system (HD72 Uniform National Projection System). If a scanned map did not have a coordinate system, we performed georeferencing using the QGIS GDAL georeferencing module, with Thin Plate Spline transformation and Nearest Neighbour resampling settings. We manually vectorized the land cover categories from the scanned and georeferenced maps using QGIS software. We standardized the data content of the vector polygon layers derived from maps with different scales. During processing, we defined a minimum patch size of 2 hectares, meaning that patches smaller than this were not displayed on the map. We merged these small patches into the surrounding larger patches and consolidated the scattered objects.

In our research, we examined six dates using the following maps and satellite imagery: 1) Maps from the First Military Survey (1783–84, 1:28,800, no projection), 2) Maps of the Second Military Survey (1859, 1:28,800, Cassini-Soldner projection), 3) Maps of the Third Military Survey (1880, 1:25,000, polyhedral projection), 4) 1950–52 Hungarian Military Survey (1:25,000, Gauss-Krüger projection), 5) Hungarian civilian topographic maps from 1990 to 1999 (1:10,000, HD72 Uniform National Projection System), and Croatian topographic maps from 1996–2000 (1:25,000, HTRS96/Croatia TM projection from the State Geodetic Administration of Croatia), 6) 2018 NÖSZTÉP (Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystem Services in Hungary) GIS layer for the Hungarian territory, and 2018 Sentinel-2 imagery (ground resolution: 10 meters) for the Croatian territories.

We identified 8 land-use categories in the study area: 1) Water surface: Rivers and standing waters with permanent water coverage or coverage present for most of the year (including gravel and sand bars), 2) Wetland: An area covered with reeds, sedges, rushes, or other herbaceous vegetation, with fluctuating water coverage or a high groundwater level, 3) Forest: A contiguous area with woody vegetation, regardless of stand composition or age, 4) Shrubland: An area covered with shrubs and dense undergrowth, 5) Grassland: Meadows and pastures, 6) Arable land: An area subject to regular (at least annual) agricultural tillage, used for the cultivation of crops, 7)

Garden, orchard: Vineyards, orchards, and gardens, 8) Built-up area: The inner areas of settlements, and groups of residential and commercial buildings in outlying areas.

4 Results

4.1 Historical landscape change data

The maps of the First Military Survey (1783–84) clearly show the condition of the Drava River before its regulation: the river meandered extensively and contained numerous islands. Land cover ratios indicate a high degree of naturalness: open water surfaces accounted for 20.5%, and wetlands for 6.1% (Figure 2 and 3). Forests formed the landscape matrix at 56.8%, the continuous, closed forest blocks typical of the floodplain were interrupted only in places by arable fields covering 7.9% of the area. The 8.6% share of grasslands is lower than in surrounding areas because forest grazing provided fodder, so there was no need to establish meadows and pastures. The proportion of built-up areas, vineyards, gardens, and orchards is negligible, only Révfülopy can be considered an exception.

The maps of the Second Military Survey (1859) already show signs of channel control measures (the straightening of river bends). In the first half of the 19th century, the settlements along the Drava were hit by several major floods. The Royal Commission for the Regulation of the Drava was set up in 1833. Its tasks included the construction of a drainage canal network, embankments, roads, and railways (Purger and Purger, 2019). In 1859 the extent of open water surfaces, bars (18.8%) and wetlands (5.6%) remained nearly constant, but forests decreased to 18.2%. The importance of crop production and livestock farming rose, so the proportion of arable land rose to 31.2% and that of grasslands to 26%, and stall-fed livestock keeping became common. Grazing intensified the erosion of soils and the islands. To prevent this, forests were planted. As a result of these regulations, the river's gradient increased, water flow accelerated, and consequently, erosion intensified in the long term, causing the groundwater level to drop (Lovász 1972).

The land-use data from the Third Military Survey (1880) showed no significant change compared to the previous survey. The proportion of water bodies was 23.4% and that of wetlands 7.3%, indicating only a minimal growth. Forests reached their smallest extent (12.2%), while grasslands dropped to 18%. Approximately 40% of the forests and nearly 30% of the grasslands were converted to cropland over the course of a few decades. Built-up areas also increased (to 0.2%), mainly due to the spread of residential and farm buildings and farmsteads in outlying areas, such as near Donji Miholjac.

The riverbed was further modified in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. From 1895 to 1915, water control works were carried out over more than 100 km from Zákány to the mouth of the river. From 1920, the Drava became a border river, so further activities were halted, and only the most necessary repairs were carried out (Károlyi 1973).

From the 1950s onward, the Iron Curtain isolated the region, thereby allowing natural vegetation to spread. A

Figure 2. Land cover of the studied area at three dates (1783-84, 1880, 2018).

turning point in land cover can be observed in the 1950s, particularly with regard to forests. The proportion of forests nearly doubled, rising to 23.7%, mainly due to the natural succession on unproductive arable land. Open water surfaces covered 20.1%, and wetlands 2.8%. The proportion of arable land (36.3%) and grasslands (16.8%) showed a slight decrease. Built-up areas increased to 0.4%.

Starting in the 1970s, barrages were built on the Yugoslav section (after Austria implemented several dams on the Upper Drava). Due to the decline in sediment transport, river channel incision accelerated, a process further intensified by gravel mining in the riverbed. The islands, shoals, and shallows or fords began to disappear. In 1989, the idea of a joint Yugoslav-Hungarian national park was raised, but it failed due to the Yugoslav Wars.

Significant changes are evident in Hungarian and Croatian maps produced between 1990 and 2000: land cover ratios began to approach the 18th-century levels. Forest cover increased to 45%. In the areas between the embankments (active floodplain), flood levels regularly resulted in water coverage critical for arable farming, so the area of arable land was reduced to 25%, while that of grasslands to 12.2%. Open water surfaces and wetlands also declined, the first by 16.2% and the latter by 1.5%. The river began to meander again, forming bends that are larger than those of previous decades.

During the 21st century, changes in land cover slowed down (Figure 3). The extent of forests reached 48.3%, the proportion of water bodies and croplands remained essentially unchanged compared to the previous period, while that of grasslands continued to decline (to 3.5%), while shrublands (3.9%) mainly replaced former meadows, pastures, and silted-up oxbow lakes.

Figure 3. Changes in land cover ratios in the study area (Ed.: G. Németh).

4.2 Landscape-level landscape metrics

Among the landscape metrics, the landscape-level curve for the Number of Patches (NP) generally fluctuates, but clearly shows lower values at the beginning and end of the study period (Figure 4). It reached its peak in 1859, as regulations led to the formation of numerous isolated oxbow lakes at that time, and the continuity of forest patches was interrupted by grasslands and arable fields. Between 1859 and 1950–52, the NP decreased due to the expansion of large-scale arable fields. The slight increase in the index during the second half of the 20th century can be linked to the growth of forest patches. Over the past three decades, the landscape has shifted back toward homogenization due to increased forest cover and the aggregation of patches, resulting in a decline of the index value.

The graphs of Shannon Diversity (SHDI) and Edge Density (ED) initially (up to 1880) correlated with each other (Figure 5). A steep rise was followed by a slight decline. The SHDI reached its peak in 1859, when the landscape was extremely diverse, containing a significant number of both

Figure 4. Changes in the landscape-level Number of Patches (NP) (Ed.: G. Németh).

Figure 5. Changes in the landscape-level Shannon Diversity (SHDI) and Edge Density (ED) (Ed.: G. Németh).

Figure 6. Changes in the landscape-level Mean Fractal Dimension (MFRACT) (Ed.: G. Németh).

artificially created patches and natural habitats, and the proportion of edges remained high. After 1880, we observe a slow but steady decline in the SHDI, as the landscape structure became more uniform, initially due to large-scale arable fields and later due to forest regeneration. No increase in diversity was observed in the post-communist period either, the index continued to stagnate. The ED, however, peaked at this time. This may be explained by the fact that grasslands and arable fields were often wedged between newly forested patches, thereby increasing edge density.

The Mean Fractal Dimension (MFRACT) showed a consistently rising trend, correlated with Edge Density (ED) ($R^2 = 0.76$) (Figure 6). A slight stagnation is observable between 1859 and 1880, which resulted from the widespread emergence of compact-shaped arable fields and the simplified planform of the main Drava channel.

5 Discussion and conclusions

The results of a study on changes in land cover within the floodplain of the Drava River between Potony (Detkovac) and Alsószentmárton (Podgajci Podravski) clearly reflect the unique dynamics of river floodplains in the Carpathian

Basin. According to 18th–19th-century maps, the area was characterized by extensive floodplain forests, while arable land was primarily limited to higher-lying areas. As a result of 19th-century river regulation and flood control projects, the expansion of arable land intensified but did not become exclusive. From the 1950s onward, we can observe a renewed expansion of forests. Most of the formerly extensive marshlands have become scrubby as a result of the decline in livestock grazing. Landscape metrics analyses show that the Number of Patches (NP) and Shannon Diversity (SHDI) increased briefly at the beginning of the study period. This was followed by a gradual decline due to the previously described re-arrangement of the landscape. The initial expansion of arable land increased diversity, followed by a decline, and the landscape structure began to revert to a state similar to that of the 18th century.

The section of the Drava River's active floodplain under study is currently part of the Mura-Drava-Danube UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. From a nature conservation perspective, it can be considered a positive development that, over the past century, the proportion of forest cover has increased, while the proportion of arable land has been

reduced significantly in the area. From an ecological and nature conservation perspective, another positive change over the past half-century is the formation of larger, ecologically more stable, and more resilient semi-natural areas. However, this is in conflict with the interests of flood control and water management. Forests located in active floodplains obstruct the passage of high discharges and can add to flood risk. In the future, consultations between nature conservation agencies and the water management directorates are expected to determine the land cover conditions of active floodplains.

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